

EFFECTIVENESS OF *DISCOVERY LEARNING* STRATEGY IN LITERATURE APPRECIATION LECTURE TO IMPROVE INTRAPERSONAL AND INTERPERSONAL INTELLIGENCE OF UKI TORAJA STUDENTS BASED ON HUMANISTIC LEARNING THEORY

Dina Gasong ^{1*} and Selvi Rajuaty Tandiseru ²

¹ Master of Language Education Study Program, Universitas Kristen Indonesia Toraja, Indonesia. *Corresponding Author Email: dinagasong@ukitoraja.ac.id

² Mathematics Education, Universitas Kristen Indonesia Toraja, Indonesia.
Email: selvirajuatytandiserumat@gmail.com

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Abstract

Communication skills are needed in every job, including that of an educator. Communication skills are acquired slowly but through much listening, observing, and reading practice. Many people have brilliant ideas but need to improve at communicating them. Thomas J. Stanley's research shows that a person's success at work is attributed to good interpersonal skills, which rank third after honesty, which ranks first, followed by discipline. IQ ranks 21st. Based on this data, it is crucial to learn communication skills. This communication factor is determined by the ability to know oneself and to understand others (intrapersonal and interpersonal). Formal education organized by the government has identified three factors that should be addressed in education. These three factors are (1) cognitive, (2) affective, and (3) psychomotor. Over the years, they have been implemented at different levels of education. Teachers in primary schools, junior high schools, and high schools have already implemented these three factors. In addition, through the Ministry of Education and Culture, the government continues to improve and has identified 18 aspects that can holistically shape students. These eighteen character aspects include religiosity, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, friendliness and communicativeness, love of peace, love of reading, concern for the environment, social awareness, and responsibility. The three educational domains, cognitive, affective, and psychomotor, are reflected in the 18 aspects proposed by the Ministry of Education and Culture. Although efforts have been made to ensure that education can address these three domains, daily reality shows that the younger generation does not need help to communicate effectively. They have yet to understand themselves and their abilities. Observations indicate that the younger generation needs to express their ideas more effectively. They struggle to stand before the class, even when simply greeting and expressing their hopes. For instance, when asking students to open or close a lecture, they still struggled to stand and deliver greetings and their expectations, even when promised a bonus or an increase in their grades. Therefore, there is a need to cultivate the skill or ability to understand oneself and others to achieve practical communication skills. It is suspected that this condition is not recognized early, particularly in primary education. This research aims first to describe the problem of students' low ability to express their ideas effectively. Second, it aims to design a humanistic learning model that can be implemented in lectures to help students understand themselves and others (interpersonal and intrapersonal). The research combines qualitative and quantitative research methods, following these steps: observation (field visits), distributing questionnaires, interviews, focus group discussions (FGDs), qualitative and quantitative data analysis, and finally, producing a research report.

Keywords: Model Development, Humanistic Learning, Intelligence, Intrapersonal, Interpersonal, College Students

INTRODUCTION

Delivering lecture materials in front of the class requires strategies or methods that align with the subject's characteristics. Additionally, it is equally important to consider the characteristics of the students attending the lecture. The conditions of students three decades ago are no longer the same as those of today's students. Various

advancements have been made, rendering the previously effective teaching models irrelevant to the characteristics of today's students.

In recent years, various learning models have been developed and implemented in classroom settings, such as active, student-oriented, contextual, collaborative, and constructivist learning. These learning models encourage students to construct their knowledge actively. It is hoped that students can shape themselves positively and become well-rounded individuals.

In general, national education aims to enlighten the lives of the nation's people and develop Indonesian individuals holistically. This means individuals who have faith and fear of the Almighty God, possess noble character, knowledge and skills, spiritual and physical health, independent personalities, and exhibit social and national responsibilities.

A civilized nation can be formed through education. The noble goal of education is to create a prosperous and civilized society. Such a society only emerges after a long and continuous nurturing process, starting at an early age. Therefore, the world of education is expected to play a significant role in producing a just, civilized, and humane generation for the nation.

With the issuance of various government policies and the noble goals of education, it is hoped that Indonesia today will be better than in previous years. There will be more tolerance and wisdom. The ultimate goal of education is to develop intelligent and God-fearing Indonesian individuals. Through education, Indonesians will appreciate diversity more. It is lovely to live in peace and harmony in Indonesia. All of this can only be achieved through education.

Although various policies and learning models have been implemented, the reality in the field shows that students still need to express their ideas and thoughts effectively. The aspirations and goals of education still need to be realized. We still witness events that do not respect humanity. We still encounter saddening conditions and situations where students cannot express their ideas and thoughts politely in public. They struggle to convey their thoughts and feelings effectively in the classroom. We come across students who are unwilling to work hard but desire good grades. Students need more motivation to excel. These conditions have been observed in classrooms in recent years.

This situation calls for reflection to improve the learning models. Perhaps the learning models being used are no longer suitable for the characteristics of students born in the era of convenience, the millennial era. They no longer know typewriters but only play with their fingertips, as they can access everything. Therefore, learning models that are appropriate for the characteristics of today's students are needed.

The nation's aspirations for a just, wealthy, and prosperous country, as stated in the 1945 Constitution, have yet to be fully realized. Education has placed more emphasis on the cognitive domain and neglected the other two aspects, namely affective and psychomotor. This is the basis for this research.

Based on the previous discussion, the specific objectives of this research are to discover and describe a learning model to enhance intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence. The second specific objective is to produce a scientific article to be published in reputable educational journals, both nationally and internationally.

This research is fundamental because if interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence are not developed, future workers may quickly become discouraged, lack creativity, and show concern for others and their environment. As a result, they may need help to work with others in their profession. It is, therefore, vital that this research be carried out. This research can only be achieved by integrating the humanities, social culture, and education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Development

Development can be defined as an improvement. It is an effort to enhance the capabilities of individuals, including technical, conceptual, and moral capabilities, to improve their quality based on their needs through education or training. Therefore, development can be achieved through formal education, non-formal education, and informal education. Therefore, what can be developed for successful educational purposes is a learning model. Learning models need to be developed because they need to be tailored to the characteristics of the subject, the learners, and the changing times.

The development of a learning model should be a systematic and logical process. By logical, it means that the design of the developed learning should take into account the potential and competencies of the learners¹. The design should determine everything that will be implemented in the learning activities. Therefore, learning development should be more realistic and applicable to real-life situations. Thus, it can be concluded that learning development is an effort to improve the quality of the learning process and outcomes, both in terms of content, methods, and substance. In terms of content, it means that teaching materials should be adjusted to the learners' knowledge development, while methodologically and substantively, it is related to the development of learning strategies, both theoretically and practically².

In researching development, the steps taken are to develop a new product or improve an existing product responsibly. The purpose of development research is to produce new products through development. Thus, development refers to the process of turning existing potential into something better and more useful. On the other hand, research and development are processes or steps to develop an existing product into an accountable product³.

2. Learning Models

The implementation of teaching and learning is always based on a model. The function of a learning model is to serve as a guide for learners in the implementation of their learning process. In addition, a learning model also serves as a guide for instructional designers in planning and implementing teaching and learning activities so that the predetermined learning objectives can be achieved. It can therefore be concluded that a learning model is a pattern or plan that can be used to operationalize the curriculum. For instructional designers, the adaptation of learning materials is aimed at guiding learners to learn in a classroom setting. According to Tiwi Pratiwi, the learning model plays a strategic role in increasing the success of the teaching and learning process. With the right learning model, it is expected that teachers will be able to deliver the material effectively and that learners will be enthusiastic about learning. Thus, a learning model can be defined as a pattern or design that encompasses the entire

process of presenting instructional materials, including planning, implementation, and the learning outcomes achieved by learners with the help of relevant facilities.

3. Learning Model Development

The development of a learning model is based on existing learning models. The learning model should be adapted to the characteristics of the subject, especially the characteristics of the learners. The development of a learning model is based on a theory, such as behaviorist theory, cognitive theory, humanistic theory, or constructivist theory.

In the development of a learning model, the 4-D approach is known. Development using the 4-D model was introduced by S. Thagarajan et al.; it includes (1) definition, (2) design, (3) development, and (4) dissemination. If these steps are adopted, it can be referred to as the 4-D approach, which is to define, design, develop, and disseminate.

The defining stage is related to the formulation of learning objectives derived from the analysis of students, tasks, and concepts. The design stage involves the preparation of a prototype of the teaching tool, which consists of three steps: (a) the development of criteria-referenced tests; (b) the selection of media; and (c) the selection of formats.

The development stage includes (a) validation of the device by experts, followed by revisions; (b) simulation, which involves operationalizing the curriculum; and (c) limited trials with actual students.

The dissemination stage involves the use of the developed device on a larger scale, e.g., in other classrooms, to test the effectiveness of its use in learning activities.

Borg and Gall suggested research and development steps: (1) potential and problems; (2) data collection; (3) product design; (4) design validation; (5) design revision; (6) product testing; (7) product revision; (8) use testing; (9) product revision; and (10) mass production. Meanwhile, Endang Mulyaty Ningsih uses the ADDIE model developed by Dick and Cary, which stands for *analysis, design, development or production, implementation or delivery, and evaluation*.

4. Humanistic Learning

The basic principle of humanistic learning is meaningfulness. From this principle, learning that humanizes individuals is developed. Therefore, humanistic learning views humans as free subjects who determine the direction of their lives. This means that humans are fully responsible for their own lives and those of others.

In humanistic learning, according to Uci Sanusi (2013)⁴, the more appropriate methods to use are dialogic, reflective, and expressive. The dialogic approach means that learners should be able to think critically and creatively together. Thus, the educator is not someone who knows everything but rather a facilitator and dialogue partner. Reflective means that learners should be able to have a dialogue with themselves. Lastly, expressive means directing learners to express their potential, actualize themselves, and realize their abilities.

In humanistic learning, teachers assist learners in self-development, attitude formation, and value clarification. The emphasis in humanistic learning is on how to establish personal communication and relationships between individuals and between individuals and groups within the educational community. Intensive relationships will

yield educational outcomes. With personal relationships, optimal development can take place. For relationships to develop optimally, it is necessary to be in an atmosphere of unconditional love, a heart full of understanding, and effective personal relationships.

5. Intelligence

In general, intelligence refers to the abilities possessed by an individual. More specifically, intelligence can be defined as a person's mental capacity to solve problems they face and to produce something in society. According to Gardner (2003) in his book "*Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*", every individual has multiple intelligences, including verbal-linguistic intelligence, logical-mathematical intelligence, visual-spatial intelligence, rhythmic-musical intelligence, bodily-kinesthetic intelligence, interpersonal intelligence, intrapersonal intelligence, naturalistic intelligence, and existential intelligence⁵.

6. Intrapersonal

Amstrong, as cited by Theresia⁶, defines this intelligence as self-knowledge and the ability to act adaptively based on that knowledge. It involves having an accurate self-image (recognizing one's strengths and weaknesses), being aware of one's moods, intentions, motivations, temperaments, and desires, as well as having self-discipline and self-esteem. Yoanitha Sandry Agustini⁷ further adds that individuals with intrapersonal intelligence are capable of experiencing various passions, enthusiasm, and spontaneity. They can be assertive, have self-worth, acknowledge their pain, possess what is needed to maintain intentions in work and relationships, and have the ability to be creative and establish close relationships. They are also capable of being alone.

Gardner, as mentioned by dalam Fitri Mares Effendi⁸, describes intrapersonal intelligence as the ability that is related but directed inward.

Characteristics of Intrapersonal Intelligence

Intrapersonal intelligence can be identified through several characteristics as proposed by Campbell et al., as cited by Theresia⁹: (1) Awareness of one's emotional domain, (2) Finding ways and outlets to express feelings and thoughts, (3) Developing an accurate self-model, (4) Motivated to identify and pursue personal goals, (5) Constructing and living by an ethical value system, (6) Working independently, (7) Curiosity about significant questions regarding the meaning, relevance, and purpose of life, (8) Continuously organizing learning and personal development goals, (9) Seeking and understanding their own spiritual experiences, (10) Gaining insights into the complexity of self and human existence, (11) Striving for self-actualization, (12) Empowering others (having a sense of humanitarian responsibility).

1. Interpersonal

Interpersonal intelligence is the ability to understand other people. Gardner, as mentioned by Theresia¹⁰, states that interpersonal intelligence is the ability to understand others, what motivates them, how they work, and how to collaborate with them. Ade Dwi Utami (2009)¹¹ concludes that interpersonal intelligence is the ability to understand others, perceive and comprehend differences in mood, temperament, motivation, and desires of others, as well as the ability to behave, communicate, and socialize among many people. Dimensions of Interpersonal Intelligence The

dimensions of interpersonal intelligence include three aspects: (1) *Social sensitivity*; (2) *Social insight*; and (3) *Social communication*.

METHOD

The method used in this research is descriptive-qualitative research. This method is conducted in a natural setting, and the data collected is qualitative. Qualitative research is based on a phenomenological philosophy that emphasizes experiencing. This qualitative method is used by integrating it with a quality learning process that follows national and international standards. Implementing this method is associated with a humanistic approach to learning.

The steps used in the development research of the Humanistic Learning Model adopt Dick and Cary's ADDIE theory, which stands for *analysis, design, development or production, implementation or delivery, and evaluation*.

The research on the development of the humanistic learning model to enhance intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence focuses on two stages: the preliminary stage and the formative evaluation stage.

1. Preliminary stage

In this stage, the researcher will determine the location and subjects of the research by contacting the school principal and subject teachers at the chosen school. Furthermore, the researcher will make other preparations, such as arranging the research schedule and establishing collaboration procedures with the classroom teachers involved in the study.

2. Formative Evaluation Stage

- a) Self-Evaluation: The analysis in this stage is the initial step in the development research. The researcher will analyze the students, the curriculum, and the materials or resources that will be developed.
- b) Design: In this stage, the researcher will design the tools or resources to be developed, including the framework, objectives, and methods. The design results can then be validated using existing validation techniques, such as triangulation of data, where the design is validated by experts and peers. The outcome of this design phase is referred to as the prototype.
- c) Prototyping: The design results of the prototype, based on self-evaluation, are presented to experts for review and students for one-on-one testing. The feedback from both sources is used for revision. The revised outcome of the prototype is referred to as the second prototype.
- d) Expert Review: In the expert review stage, the designed product is examined, evaluated, and assessed by experts. These experts evaluate the content and language of each prototype. The suggestions from the experts are used to revise the tools. At this stage, the feedback and suggestions from the experts (validators) regarding the design are documented on a validation sheet for revision purposes and to determine the validity of the design.
- e) One-to-one: In the one-to-one stage, the researcher tests the developed design with individual students or teachers acting as testers. The results of this implementation are used to revise the design that has been created.

- f) **Small Group:** The revisions based on the feedback from experts and the difficulties encountered during the testing of the prototype serve as the basis for revising the prototype, which is then referred to as the second prototype. The second prototype is then tested with a small group. The results of this implementation are used for further revision before the field test. The design revisions based on the feedback and comments from the respondents in the small group and the analysis of the test items are referred to as the third prototype.
- g) **Field Test:** The suggestions and results from the testing of the second prototype are used to revise the design of the second prototype. The revised prototype is then tested with the research subjects as a field test. The product that has been tested in the field must meet quality criteria. According to Akker (1999), the three criteria for quality are validity, practicality, and effectiveness (having potential effects).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Intrapersonal Intelligence Data:

No	Intelligence	Percentage
1	Self-awareness (emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, independence, and self-actualization) indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowing who you are and your feelings and using that self-knowledge smartly and positively. 	60
2	Knowing what is desired (skill in setting clear goals, so there are clear benchmarks to achieve) indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having a list of goals. • Setting SMART criteria (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely). • Expressing goals in a positive form. • Creating sensors to detect your goals. • Aligning your goals. • Respect others. • Ask questions that test your goals. 	70
3	Knowing the importance of continuous learning indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognizing the value of lifelong learning. 	50

2. Interpersonal Intelligence Data:

No	Intelligence	Score
1	Social sensitivity (prosocial behavior: moral actions that should be performed culturally, such as sharing, helping someone in need, cooperating with others, and expressing sympathy)	60
2	Social insight (the ability of an individual to understand and seek effective solutions to problems within a social interaction so that the problem does not hinder or destroy the established social relationship)	60
3	Social communication (the ability of an individual to use communication processes to establish and build healthy interpersonal relationships)	60

3. Interpretation of Findings:

Based on the questionnaire, interviews, and observations with students, it can be concluded that the condition of the students is that they are unable to have a good understanding of themselves and others. This is evident from the lack of sensitivity among students towards others and themselves. Generally, they tend to blame others if they are not successful instead of reflecting on themselves and why such situations occur. Students are only concerned about getting good grades but are unwilling to work hard. They complete assignments hastily and carelessly. They dare to call their

professors and judge why they received a poor grade, and when the professor shows the actual grade, it is even lower than the grade they expected. When it comes to group assignments, they are unprepared for the presentation of the paper. On the other hand, when it comes to individual assignments, they claim to have many other tasks to do.

Once everything was understood, an intervention was carried out by providing examples of polite behavior in communicating with elderly people and communicating politely with professors. The professors responded politely to every student's WhatsApp messages. As a result, the students realized that they had exhibited inappropriate behavior and apologized for their actions. Additionally, the professors emphasized the importance of maintaining cleanliness in the classroom because students would often throw tissue papers, candy wrappers, and drink containers carelessly in the classroom, which could be quite irritating. However, the professors implemented a method where students were required to start the lecture by standing in front of the class and delivering a message similar to flight attendants on an airplane, emphasizing the importance of cleanliness. If students disregarded this requirement, they would be fined an amount ranging from 2000 to 5000, depending on the agreement. The fines collected were handed over to the class treasurer to be used for class needs, such as photocopying course materials and other expenses. After three semesters, the students began to realize the importance of cleanliness and punctuality in attending lectures. Previously, there were always students who arrived late and joined the class halfway through.

The model implemented in humanistic learning focuses on the following principles: (1) Guiding students at the beginning of the class with a respectful and friendly approach, providing them with a clear understanding of what needs to be prepared for the future. (2) Offering positive feedback to students when they have completed their assignments. This involves using encouraging words such as "great" or "outstanding" for those who have done well and providing words of motivation like "keep going, you can do it" for those who may need improvement. However, if a student tries to corner the professor by claiming that they received a poor grade, the actual grade will be shown to them, helping them realize that they were assisted to pass. (3) Expressing gratitude for students' efforts and apologizing for any mistakes made by the professor. These models can be utilized to implement humanistic approaches in the learning process.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the research findings suggest that learning with a humanistic approach is highly effective in developing students' interpersonal and intrapersonal skills. Therefore, it is recommended for educators apply this approach in their teaching practices.

Footnotes

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